

Comparison of the Performance of Commercially Introduced Wheat Varieties with Approved Ones in Terms of Water Requirement in Production Characteristics

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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted in the city of Diwaniyah, located at 44.89 degrees longitude and 32.01 degrees latitude, for the 2022-2023 agricultural season. The aim was to evaluate the performance of commercially introduced wheat genotypes with approved varieties in terms of water requirements, productivity, and quality characteristics. The experiment was implemented using a split-plot method using a Randomized Complete Block Design (R.C.B.D). Five irrigation treatments were applied to the main plots (spate irrigation and 100% water ration for wheat, 90% water ration, 80% water ration, and 70% water ration). Eight cultivars were applied to the sub plots of the experimental units (Ibaa 99, Buhuth 22, Jad, Shawmbi, Afanto, Sanzio, R Arabiya, and Wafiya), with three replicates. The results showed a significant difference between the irrigation treatments. The flood irrigation treatment significantly outperformed the other treatments for plant height, while the 80% water ration and 100% water ration treatments yielded the highest average flag leaf area. Plants receiving 70% water ration treatment yielded the highest average number of tillers, grain yield, biological yield, and harvest index, while plants receiving 80% water ration treatment yielded the highest average 1000-grain weight. The results showed significant differences between the approved and introduced wheat genotypes. Abaa 99 cultivar had the highest average plant height. The Wafiya cultivar also recorded the highest average flag leaf area. Sanzio cultivar excelled, recording the highest average number of tillers, 1000-grain weight, grain yield, biological yield, and harvest index. The interaction between the two factors had a significant effect on the studied traits. The combination (Sanzio X 80% water ration) achieved the highest average number of tillers, 1000-grain weight, and grain yield.

Keywords: *Commercially, wheat varieties, water requirement, production characteristics.*

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Introduction

The scarcity of water used for agricultural purposes is one of the most important problems facing many countries around the world today, especially Iraq. The expansion of this crop's production will increase in the coming years (Hashem, 2016).

In the face of this major challenge, much effort has been focused on addressing this problem, which is becoming more acute in various parts of the world. The decline in the water level of the Tigris and Euphrates rivers has had a significant impact on the reduction of cultivated areas. This requires screening existing varieties, identifying the most drought-tolerant varieties, and improving the environment surrounding the crop by using the best soil and crop management practices (Mohammed, 2000).

Iraq is among the countries that have focused on this aspect in specialized research centers, to develop new genetic lines with superior productivity and quality traits through breeding and improvement programs, identify those best suited to the new reality, includes adopting introduction programs as one of the methods used, to obtain the best genetic compositions in terms of coexistence with the local environment. This is done by subjecting these varieties to numerous tests and determining the stability of their traits across successive generations. Recently, several varieties have been introduced to the market, traded, and cultivated. Their high yields from their parent seeds have not been considered. This has not been done to investigate the possibility of their superior productivity traits continuing across generations (Al-Salem, 2018).

Therefore, this experiment aimed to determine the performance of some approved and commercially introduced varieties in the local environment, to determine their water requirements and the impact this has on the stability of their productivity traits.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site

A field experiment was conducted in a field located in the Al-Daghara District of Diwaniyah Governorate, located 14 km north of the governorate center, during the 2022-2023 agricultural season. A set of random soil samples were taken at a depth of 0-30 cm. The samples were thoroughly mixed, passed through sieves with 2 mm diameter holes, Air-dried, then ground. A single composite sample was taken to assess the physical and chemical properties of the soil (Table 1). The aim was to determine the performance of approved and commercially introduced varieties in terms of water requirements, productivity, and quality.

Table 1. Some Chemical and Physical Properties of the Experimental Soil before Planting*

Items	Value	Unit
Chemical properties	pH	7.80
	ECe	5.30
	Available nitrogen	0.02
	Available Phosphorus	2.40
	Available Potassium	10.60
Physical properties	Sand	22.50
	Silt	37.50
	Clay	40.50
Soil texture	Silty loam	

Note: *The analyses were conducted in the laboratory of the Diwaniyah Agriculture Directorate/Ministry of Agriculture.

Experimental Factors

The experiment included the study of two factors:

First: Five irrigation levels distributed across the main plots:

L1: Spate irrigation treatment.

L2: Wheat water ration treatment.

L3: 90% of the water ration.

L4: 80% of the water ration.

L5: 70% of the water ration.

Irrigation was carried out using Shatt Al-Daghara water and a plastic pipe network connected to an electric submersible pump, equipped with a meter to measure the amount of water added to each experimental unit and each stage of plant growth (Al-Saedi, 2012), varied rates were applied according to plant needs (Table 2).

Table 2. Irrigation Levels during the Growing Season

Irrigation levels	Ratio (%)	Flood irrigation	Water requirement for wheat crop (L. m ⁻²)	70% of the water ration (L. m ⁻²)	80% of the water ration (L. m ⁻²)	90% of the water ration (L. m ⁻²)
L1	18.67	-	70.23	35.39	50.56	63.19
L2	25.41	-	95.59	48.17	68.82	86.01
L3	29.51	-	111.01	55.95	79.92	99.89
L4	18.67	-	70.23	35.39	50.56	63.19
L5	7.70	-	28.96	14.59	20.85	23.69
Total			376.02	189.49	270.71	335.97

Second: Wheat varieties: The experiment included eight varieties of soft wheat placed in secondary panels, namely the variety Aba 99 and Buhuth 22 (varieties approved by the Ministry of Agriculture), and the introduced varieties Jad, Shaumbi, Ufanto, Vi Sanzio, Arabiya R, and the variety Wafih (commercial varieties), (Table 3).

Table 3. Varieties and Genotypes Used in the Experiment

No.	Varieties	Field symbol	Equipment supplier	Source
1	Ibaa 99	V1	Agricultural Research Department, Projects Division	Approved
2	Buhuth 22	V2	Agricultural Research Department, Projects Division	Approved
3	Jad	V3	Commercial agricultural companies	Germany
4	Shawmbi	V4	Commercial agricultural companies	USA
5	Afanto	V5	Commercial agricultural companies	Italy
6	Sanzio	V6	Commercial agricultural companies	Italy
7	Arabiya	V7	Commercial agricultural companies	Italy
8	Wafiya	V8	Commercial agricultural companies	French

Experimental Design

Based on the nature of the factors involved in the experiment and the soil type, the experiment was conducted using a split-plot method using a randomized complete block design (R.C.B.D) with three replicates. Each replicate contained 40 experimental units. Irrigation treatments were placed in the main plots, and cultivars were placed in the sub plots.

Agricultural Operations

The experimental land was plowed twice perpendicularly with a rototille, after irrigation, it was then smoothed using disc harrows. The soil was then leveled using a leveling machine. The number of experimental units reached 120, with three replicates, each replicate contained 40 experimental units. The dimensions of each experimental unit were 1×1 m, it included five lines, each 1 m long, with a distance of 20 cm between each line. The distance between each experimental unit was 50 cm. The distance between replicates was 2 m. A 2 m gap was left between the main plots.

Wheat seeds were planted in late November, at a seed quantity of 120 kg ha⁻¹ (Guidance Bulletin, 2012), in rows. Fertilizer recommendations were added to the application of urea (46%) as a nitrogen source, at a quantity of 200 kg N ha⁻¹, in four equal batches. The first was applied during the emergence, branching, elongation, and lining stages. Phosphate fertilizer was added in the form of triple superphosphate (P) at a rate of 80 kg ha⁻¹ in a single batch before planting (Jadoua, 1995). Potassium fertilizer was also added in the form of potassium sulfate (42%), in two equal batches, the first after emergence and the second at the branching stage, at a rate of 60 kg ha⁻¹ (Al-Taher, 2005). Irrigation and weeding were carried out as needed.

Traits Studied

Plant height (cm), lag leaf area (cm²), Number of tillers (m²), 1000-grain weight (gm), Grain yield (tons/ha), Biological yield, and Harvest index.

Results and Discussion

Plant Height (cm)

Table 4 shows a significant effect of cultivars, water ration, and their interaction on plant height (cm). The spate irrigation treatment (L1) significantly outperformed the other treatments for plant height (88.86 cm), while the L4 (80% water ration) and L5 (70% water ration) treatments had the lowest average (79.18 cm), L5 (80% water ration) treatment was considered one of the main determinants of vegetative growth, it influences plant height due to its association with the length and shortness of the growth period, reaching its maximum.

The results showed that wheat cultivars differed significantly in plant height. The cultivar Ibaa 99 had the highest average plant height (90.70 cm), surpassing all other cultivars included in the study, without a significant difference from the cultivar Buhuth 22, while the cultivar Jad produced the lowest average plant height in the first season (79.06 cm), without a significant difference from the cultivar Sanzio. The reason for the variation in average plant height among wheat cultivars is attributed to their genotype, which is primarily controlled by the action of the additive gene with respect to the length and shortness of the internodes, these results are consistent with the findings of Fadala and Al-Tahir (2023) and Al-Burki et al. (2019), who indicated differences in genetic compositions in plant height.

Regarding interaction, the results showed that the interaction between irrigation treatments and cultivars significantly affected plant height. The plants in the combination (variety Ibaa99× L1 treatment with flood irrigation) produced the highest average plant height of 98.00 cm, with no significant differences from any other combinations, while the plants in the two combinations (variety Ibaa99 × L4 treatment with 80% of the water ration) and (variety Shaombe × L5 treatment with 70% of the ration) produced the lowest average plant height of 76.10 cm for both, these differences were not significantly different from some combinations. The superiority of the aforementioned combinations can be attributed to the same reasons mentioned in the discussion of the factors, which are considered separate, given the consistency of the results.

Table 4. Effect of Water Rationing, Varieties, and Their Interaction on Plant Height (cm)

Varieties	Irrigation levels					Mean
	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	
V1	98.00	96.30	95.50	76.100	87.60	90.70
V2	96.85	92.90	92.50	82.60	87.10	90.39
V3	82.40	79.80	79.90	76.70	76.50	79.06
V4	82.90	82.30	80.60	78.20	76.10	80.02
V5	92.20	90.40	88.40	79.36	82.60	86.95
V6	81.90	81.30	79.75	78.50	76.70	79.63
V7	85.93	83.10	82.10	80.90	78.20	82.04
V8	89.30	86.80	82.75	81.15	79.09	83.81
Mean	88.86	86.61	85.18	79.18	80.48	
L.S.D _{0.05}	L		V		L×V	
	0.75		0.38		1.04	

Flag Leaf Area (cm²)

Table 5 shows a significant effect of cultivars, water rationing, and their interaction on flag leaf area (cm²). Water ration significantly affected flag leaf area. Plants in treatment L2 (100% water ration) had the highest average for this trait (49.61 cm²), with no significant difference from treatments L1 (spill irrigation), L3 (90% water ration), and L4 (80% water ration), while plants in treatment L5 (70% water ration) had the lowest average flag leaf area (44.39 cm²). The superiority of the aforementioned treatment may be due to the abundance of water, which ensures normal growth of plant parts, this leads to cell division and elongation at their normal rates, reflected in an increase in flag leaf area. This may also be due to the increased vegetative growth period, which helped increase division and elongation rates, and was reflected in the growth and expansion of the flag leaf, These results were consistent with the findings of Hashem (2012), pointed out that cell growth and division differed according to the amount of irrigation.

The results of the same table also showed differences in flag leaf area among the varieties included in the experiment. The "Wafia" variety plants recorded the highest average flag leaf area (60.97 cm²), significantly superior to the other varieties included in the experiment, while the "Shawmbi" variety plants recorded the lowest average flag leaf area (35.33 cm²). The reason for the variation in genetic compositions in flag leaf area may be attributed to the presence of variations in their genetic nature in terms of cell division, elongation, and expansion. This is a natural result of the differences in their adaptation to the environmental conditions prevailing in the region. The origins of these genetic compositions were also different. This result was consistent with Al-Burki *et al.* (2019).

The results in the table also showed a significant interaction between water ration and cultivar levels in flag leaf area. The plants in the combination (Wafia x L1 treatment with flood irrigation) had the highest average flag leaf area of 74.64 cm² compared to a number of combinations, while the combination (Cultivar Shawmby x L4 treatment with 70% water ration) had the lowest average flag leaf area of 32.92 cm².

Table 5. The Effect of the Water Ration, the Varieties, and the Interaction between Them on the Flag Leaf Area (cm²)

Varieties	Irrigation levels					Mean
	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	
V1	47.95	44.62	46.07	40.96	50.78	46.08
V2	50.95	55.03	54.94	56.74	55.13	54.56
V3	42.62	48.26	42.35	39.44	36.23	41.78

V4	32.29	35.70	40.45	32.92	35.28	35.33
V5	46.89	39.87	61.84	60.69	40.95	50.45
V6	45.22	60.56	49.92	46.37	38.70	48.15
V7	42.23	47.13	40.52	39.06	48.71	43.53
V8	74.64	65.74	53.57	61.55	49.35	60.97
Mean	47.85	49.61	48.71	47.47	44.39	
L.S.D_{0.05}	L		V		L×V	
	2.66		5.39		11.49	

Number of Tillers (m²)

Table 6 shows a significant effect of cultivars, water ration, and their interaction on the number of tillers (m²). Water ration significantly affected the number of tillers (m²). Plants in treatment L5 (70% of the water ration) produced the highest average number of tillers (533.50 tillers. m²). There was no significant difference from treatment L4 (80% of the water ration), while plants in the L3 treatment recorded the lowest rate (459.60 tillers. m²). The reason for the increase in the number of runners with increased water rationing may be attributed to a decrease in apical dominance, through a decrease in plant height (Table 4), this led to an increase in the tillers rate, which means increased representation rates and decreased competition between parts of the same plant, This led to an increase in the number of tillers per plant, which was reflected in the number of runners per unit area.

The results also showed significant differences between the cultivars in this trait. Sanzio cultivar plants outperformed, recording the highest average number of tillers (581.80 tillers. m²), a significant difference from the other cultivars. Meanwhile, the Shawmbe cultivar recorded the highest average number of tillers (458.70 tillers. m²), outperforming the other cultivars studied. Meanwhile, the Ovanto cultivar plants produced the lowest average for this trait (422.50 tillers. m²), without a significant difference from the Arabia cultivar. The superiority of the Sanzio cultivar may be attributed to the cultivar's genetic ability to produce tillers and its ability to utilize favorable conditions to form metabolites that support tiller growth and increase their number per unit area. This result is consistent with what was reported by Jadou and Baqer (2012) and Al-Salem. (2018), in their experiments, they examined the differences between wheat varieties in this trait.

As for interaction, it had a significant effect on this trait, it was observed that the combination (Sanzio variety x L4 treatment (80% water ration) produced the highest average (701.30 tillers. m²), with a significant difference from several combinations. Meanwhile, the combination (Ibaa 99 x L5 treatment (70% water ration) recorded the lowest average, (308.30 tillers. m²), with no significant difference from several combinations. This may be due to what was mentioned in the discussion of individual factors.

Table 6. The Effect of Water Stress, Varieties and Their Interaction on the Number of Tillers (m²)

Varieties	Irrigation levels					Mean
	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	
V1	511.30	447.30	485.00	522.70	513.00	495.90
V2	443.30	628.30	475.00	463.30	550.30	512.10
V3	552.00	528.00	391.30	536.30	549.30	511.40
V4	578.30	585.30	456.30	549.00	579.30	549.70
V5	353.30	456.00	400.30	466.00	537.00	442.50
V6	536.30	499.30	561.30	701.30	610.70	581.80
V7	344.00	449.30	427.30	525.00	444.70	438.10
V8	418.30	461.30	480.00	478.00	483.30	464.20
Mean	467.10	506.90	459.60	530.20	533.50	439.50
L.S.D_{0.05}	L		V		L×V	
	6.65		26.18		55.03	

1000-Grain Weight (gm)

Table 7 shows a significant effect of cultivars, water ration, and their interaction on the 1000-grain weight (gm) trait. The results of the table revealed significant differences between the varieties included in the experiment. Sanzio variety produced the highest average thousand-grain weight (49.27 gm). This may be due to the fact that grain weight is an indicator of the efficiency of the transfer of metabolites from the source to the destination, which is related to the nature of the variety, and the rate and duration of processing of manufactured nutrients during the period from the beginning of fertilization to physiological maturity. The variation between varieties in this trait may be due to the difference in the number of grains in the spike, which led to a greater opportunity for the accumulation of nutrients in the grain, due to the lack of competition between grains within a single spike, these results were consistent with Al-Amri and Al-Obaidi (2016); Al-Hamdawi (2017); Al-Salem (2018), who demonstrated that wheat varieties differ in the thousand-grain weight trait.

Water ration significantly affected 1000-grain weight. Plants in the L4 treatment (80% water ration) yielded the highest average (47.82 gm). There was no significant difference from the L3 treatment (90% water ration), while the L2 treatment (100% water ration) yielded the lowest average (43.45 gm). The superiority of the L4 treatment (80% water ration) may be due to it being one of the treatments that demonstrated a clear balance of yield components, it experienced a slight decrease in the number of fertile spikes and the number of grains per spike. This allowed it to increase its grain weight based on the principle of compensation between yield components. This was a natural result of the lack of competition between the number of spikes per unit area and the relative number of grains, allowed for an increase in grain weight. These results are consistent with Hashem (2012).

The results showed a significant interaction between water ration and cultivars for this trait. The combination (Sanzio cultivar x L4 treatment with 80% water ration) yielded the highest average 1000-grain weight (55.27 gm), a significant difference from all combinations. Meanwhile, the combination (Shuambeii cultivar x L2 treatment with 100% water ration) yielded the highest average 1000-grain weight. The reason for the difference in response to the interaction can be attributed to the individual factors, on the one hand, and their variation from one season to the next. However, this trait is subject to the principle of compensation between yield components, whereas not all yield components can increase simultaneously, and an increase in one or two of them means that the third component will not increase.

Table 7. The Effect of Water Tension, Varieties and Their Interaction on the Weight of a 1000-Grains (gm)

Varieties	Irrigation levels					Mean
	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	
V1	45.16	45.79	48.71	49.39	49.35	47.68
V2	42.36	41.48	45.66	45.95	45.57	44.40
V3	40.27	44.30	44.01	42.45	42.46	42.70
V4	45.04	35.99	39.99	42.90	41.68	41.12
V5	45.12	44.93	50.51	51.22	47.27	47.81
V6	49.38	46.58	47.47	55.27	47.66	49.27
V7	45.57	43.23	45.83	47.18	48.59	46.08
V8	45.47	45.31	50.15	47.23	46.95	47.02
Mean	44.80	43.45	46.54	47.82	46.19	
L.S.D _{0.05}	L		V		L×V	
	1.29		1.55		3.43	

Grain Yield (tons.ha⁻¹)

Table 8 shows a significant effect of cultivars, water ration, and their interaction on grain yield. Water ration significantly affected grain yield. Plants in the L5 treatment (70% water ration) produced the highest average grain yield (9.27 tons ha⁻¹). There was no significant difference from the L4 treatment (80% water ration), while plants in the L1 treatment produced the lowest average grain yield (7.35 tons ha⁻¹). The reason for the superiority of the L5 treatment (70% water ration) in grain yield is due to its superiority in both yield components: the number of fertile spikes and the number of grains per spike, with a slight relative decrease in the thousand-grain weight. This result is consistent with Karim and Mahmoud (2021), who demonstrated the effect of abiotic stresses on wheat seed size.

The cultivars differed significantly in grain yield. Sanzio cultivar plants excelled, yielding the highest average grain yield (1024 ton.ha⁻¹), while the Ovanto cultivar plants yielded the lowest average for this trait (6.44 ton.ha⁻¹). This result is consistent with what was indicated by Al-Tahir (2014); Al-Aseel *et al.* (2018), and Al-Salem (2018), who demonstrated that wheat cultivars differ in grain yield.

The results also found a significant interaction between the two factors in this trait. The plants in the combination (Sanzio variety x treated with L4 80% water ration) produced the highest average grain yield (11.76 tons. ha⁻¹), without a significant difference from the combination (variety in Sanzio x treatment L5 70% water ration), while the combination plants (variety Jad x treatment L1 flood irrigation) showed the lowest average grain yield (4.54 ton. ha⁻¹), without a significant difference from a number of combinations. The reason for this discrepancy can be attributed to the climatic factor and its interaction, on the one hand, and the compensation relationship between the three main yield components, which differs between a single combination and between combinations of the two factors. Because the yield is the sum of the three yield components, an increase or decrease in one or more of them, leaves a significant impact on the grain yield.

Table 8. The Effect of Water Rationing, Varieties and Their Interaction on the Grain Yield (ton.ha⁻¹)

Varieties	Irrigation levels					Mean
	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	
V1	8.02	8.83	7.35	11.20	7.64	8.61
V2	7.76	9.80	6.92	5.46	11.52	8.29
V3	4.54	8.28	10.07	9.56	8.25	8.14
V4	8.26	8.03	7.82	9.08	8.92	8.42
V5	4.49	5.98	5.74	6.86	9.12	6.44
V6	8.93	10.38	9.05	11.76	11.11	10.24
V7	8.47	8.44	8.52	7.68	9.24	8.47
V8	8.35	6.36	8.18	9.40	8.37	8.13
Mean	7.35	8.26	7.96	8.87	9.27	
L.S.D _{0.05}	L		V		L×V	
	0.30		0.40		0.89	

Biological Yield (ton.ha⁻¹)

Table 9 shows a significant effect of cultivars, water ration, and their interaction on the biological yield trait (ton.ha⁻¹). Water ration significantly affected the biological yield trait. Plants in treatment L5 (70% water ration) produced the highest average biological yield (19.31 ton.ha⁻¹), while treatment L1 (spate irrigation) recorded the lowest average biological yield (16.38 ton.ha⁻¹). The superiority of the water ration L5 treatment (70% water ration) in biological yield may be due to its superiority in the number of tillers

per unit area, the number of fertile spikes per unit area, and grain yield, which jointly and primarily contribute to determining the biological yield.

The cultivars differed significantly in this trait. The "Sanzio" cultivar recorded the highest average biological yield (21.07 ton. ha⁻¹). It did not differ significantly from the "Buhuth 22" cultivar, while the "Ovanto" cultivar plants produced the lowest averages for this trait (14.00 ton. ha⁻¹). The superiority of the "Sanzio" cultivar in biological yield may be due to its superiority in flowering time, plant dry weight, number of tillers per unit area, number of fertile spikes, and grain yield. These together determine the biological yield. The differences between these cultivars in tiller production are consistent with Kadhum (2015); Al-Husseini (2016); and Muhammad *et al.* (2018). The biological yield of wheat varies depending on genotypes.

Regarding the interaction between the two factors. The plants in the combination (Bohth 22 variety x L5 treatment 70% water ration) produced the highest average biological yield (25.55 ton. ha⁻¹), with no significant differences from several combinations, while the combination (Ovanto x L1 flood irrigation variety) produced the lowest average (9.28 ton. ha⁻¹). The main factors controlling the biological yield results are grain yield and straw yield, which share the same value, with each component being subject to a set of influences. Grain yield is influenced by its components, and straw yield is influenced by most growth indicators, controlling their responses in one direction is not possible under the influence of experimental factors. This explains the trend taken by the interaction results, unlike the effect of the factors, which are individual.

Table 9. Effect of Water Ration, Varieties, and Their Interaction on the Biological Yield Trait (ton. ha⁻¹)

Varieties	Irrigation levels					Mean
	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	
V1	15.26	20.13	18.00	23.55	15.51	18.49
V2	15.55	22.97	19.81	13.21	25.55	19.46
V3	19.47	16.59	20.35	19.59	16.69	18.52
V4	16.75	17.91	17.22	18.31	17.59	17.55
V5	9.28	13.74	11.71	15.28	20.02	14.00
V6	18.11	21.14	18.59	24.25	23.27	21.07
V7	19.06	17.13	17.29	15.63	18.17	17.46
V8	17.38	14.92	17.03	19.18	17.65	17.23
Mean	16.38	18.06	17.50	18.62	19.31	
L.S.D_{0.05}	L		V		L×V	
	1.01		0.97		2.21	

Harvest Index (%)

Table 10 shows a significant effect of cultivars, water ration, and their interaction on the harvest index. The harvest index gradually increased as the amount of irrigation water decreased during the first season. Treatment L5 plants (70% of the water ration) produced the highest average harvest index (47.98%), with no significant difference from treatment L4 (80% of the water ration), while treatment L1 plants (spate irrigation) produced the lowest average (44.99%), with no significant difference from treatments L2 (100% of the water ration) and L3 (90% of the water ration), these results are consistent with the findings of Hashem (2012).

Table 10. The Effect of Water Rationing, Varieties and Their Interaction on the Harvest Index (%)

Varieties	Irrigation levels					Mean
	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	
V1	48.26	44.07	41.43	47.54	49.26	46.11
V2	47.80	42.65	35.53	41.00	45.09	42.41
V3	23.46	49.58	49.00	47.46	49.46	43.79
V4	49.72	44.78	45.42	49.57	48.63	47.62
V5	48.40	43.54	49.10	45.00	45.61	46.33
V6	49.32	49.17	48.72	48.46	49.03	48.94
V7	44.91	49.29	49.52	49.14	49.34	48.44
V8	48.38	42.74	48.03	49.04	47.45	47.13
Mean	44.99	45.73	45.84	47.15	47.98	
L.S.D _{0.05}	L		V		L×V	
	1.23		1.42		3.15	

Varieties also significantly affected this trait. Sanzio variety yielded the highest average yield index, (48.94%), without a significant difference from the Arabiya variety, while the Buhuth 22 variety plants recorded the lowest average (42.41%), without a significant difference from the Jad variety. The variation in yield index among varieties may be attributed to differences in grain yield and biological yield. The ability of genotype in terms of the efficiency of converting produced materials from the source to the destination (grain). This result is consistent with Kadhum (2015) and Noaema *et al.* (2020). The variation in yield index among varieties is attributed to differences in grain yield and biological yield. Varieties differ in their ability to distribute net photosynthesis to the destination. This result is also consistent with Al-Salem (2018), there were significant differences between wheat varieties in the harvest index.

Conclusion

Regarding the interaction between the two factors affecting the harvest index for all cultivars and in the presence of water stress. The combination (Arabic x treatment L 390% water ration) yielded the highest average harvest index (49.52%), with a significant difference from the other combinations, while the combination (variety x treatment L 100% water ration) yielded the lowest average harvest index (27.09%), without a significant difference from any other combination. This may be due to the fact that interpreting the results of the harvest index under any influencing factor focuses on the conversion efficiency of the treatment, rather than on the basis of the increase in grain yield and biological yield, because the increase in one is due to the increase in the other, since biological yield is essentially, the result of combining straw yield with grain yield. The increase in grain yield is due to an increase in biological yield, this leads us to consider the extent of the increase in conversion efficiency, the increase in the part. (Grains) in relation to the whole, of which the part (grains) constitutes an important component. In other words, how much can the plant convert its total dry matter into grains. Therefore, the superiority achieved by the aforementioned treatments and combinations is due to their conversion efficiency, not based on the increase or decrease in either side of the equation (grains and biomass).

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